

Power System Damping Using Hierarchical Fuzzy Multi- Input PSS and Communication Lines Active Power Deviations Input and SVC

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Abstract : In this paper the application of a hierarchical fuzzy system (HFS) based on MPSS and SVC in multi-machine environment is studied. Also The effect of communication lines active power variance signal between two Δ P_{Tie}-line regions, as one of the inputs of hierarchical fuzzy multi-input PSS and SVC (HFMPSS&SVC), on the increase of low frequency oscillation damping is examined. In the MPSS, to have better efficiency an auxiliary signal of reactive power deviation (ΔQ) is added with $\Delta P + \Delta \omega$ input type PSS. The number of rules grows exponentially with the number of variables in a classic fuzzy system. To reduce the number of rules the HFS consists of a number of low-dimensional fuzzy systems in a hierarchical structure. Phasor model of SVC is described and used in this paper. The performances of MPSS and Δ P_{Tie}-line based HFMPSS and also the proposed method in damping inter-area mode of oscillation are examined in response to disturbances. The efficiency of the proposed model is examined by simulating a four-machine power system. Results show that the proposed method is performing satisfactorily within the whole range of disturbances and reduces the cost of system.

Keywords : communication lines active power variance signal, Hierarchical fuzzy system (HFS), Multi-input power system stabilizer (MPSS), Static VAR compensator (SVC).

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